

Association of chorioretinal thickness with chronic kidney disease

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Abstract

Introduction:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a systemic condition that significantly affects microvascular structures, including those of the eye. The retina and choroid share similar embryologic and vascular characteristics with the kidney, making them susceptible to parallel pathological changes. Optical coherence tomography (OCT) has emerged as a valuable non-invasive tool for evaluating chorioretinal alterations in systemic diseases. This study aimed to assess chorioretinal thickness changes in patients with CKD across different stages using spectral-domain OCT (SD-OCT).

Materials and Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted over six months at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. Seventy patients with CKD aged above 18 years were enrolled. Exclusion criteria included high myopia, media opacities, retinal pathologies, and prior retinal surgeries or laser treatments. Retinal and choroidal thicknesses were measured using SD-OCT in inner and outer quadrants (nasal, superior, temporal, inferior). Systemic parameters, including estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), serum albumin, and C-reactive protein (CRP), were recorded. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 26.0, with comparisons across CKD stages performed using one-way ANOVA.

Results:

A progressive and statistically significant reduction in both retinal and choroidal thickness was observed with advancing CKD stage ($p < 0.001$). The total retinal thickness decreased from $275.57 \pm 5.56 \mu\text{m}$ in stage 1 to $243.19 \pm 11.53 \mu\text{m}$ in stage

5. Choroidal thickness also declined markedly, particularly in the inferior inner quadrant (from $368.36 \pm 9.42 \mu\text{m}$ in stage 1 to $283.19 \pm 15.80 \mu\text{m}$ in stage 5). Other parameters like IOP, MAP, and BMI did not vary significantly across groups. A strong correlation was noted between declining eGFR, elevated CRP, hypoalbuminemia, and thinning of chorioretinal layers.

Conclusion:

Chorioretinal thickness, as measured by SD-OCT, declines significantly with worsening CKD. These ocular changes reflect systemic microvascular compromise and inflammation, positioning OCT as a potential non-invasive marker for systemic disease progression in CKD. Regular ophthalmic evaluation in CKD patients may aid in early detection and holistic disease monitoring.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive and irreversible condition characterized by a decline in kidney function lasting more than three months, with or without evidence of kidney damage. It affects approximately 10% of the global adult population and is associated with significant morbidity, mortality, and health care costs. CKD is a systemic disease with widespread effects on various organs, including the eye. The kidney and the eye share similar embryological origins and microvascular architecture, making them vulnerable to common pathogenic processes such as endothelial dysfunction, microvascular ischemia, autonomic dysregulation, and chronic inflammation [1,2].

Recent research has highlighted the potential role of ocular imaging, especially optical coherence tomography (OCT). OCT is a non-invasive imaging modality that provides high-resolution cross-sectional images of retinal and choroidal layers. Spectral-domain OCT (SD-OCT) allows detailed analysis of structural changes in the retina and choroid. Previous studies have shown that patients with CKD exhibit significant thinning of the choroid and retina, likely due to microvascular damage and altered autonomic regulation [3,4]. The choroidal vasculature, rich in autonomic innervation, is particularly susceptible to systemic changes such as increased sympathetic activity, which is commonly observed in advanced stages of CKD [2,5].

Moreover, chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, and volume shifts—especially in patients undergoing dialysis—can contribute to fluctuations in choroidal thickness. Several studies have reported reduced retinal and choroidal thickness in patients on hemodialysis and those with end-stage renal disease (ESRD), underscoring the interplay between renal and ocular health [5,6]. Despite these insights, comprehensive quadrant-wise evaluation of chorioretinal thickness across different CKD stages remains limited. The present study aims to evaluate changes in

chorioretinal thickness using SD-OCT among CKD patients stratified by disease stage and to assess correlations with renal function indices.

Stages of CKD of all types		
Stage	Qualitative Description	GFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)
1	Kidney damage – normal GFR	> 90*
2	Kidney damage – mild ↓ GFR	60–89*
3a	Moderate ↓ GFR	45–59
3b	Moderate ↓ GFR	30–44
4	Severe ↓ GFR	15–29
5	End-stage renal disease	<15

*A GFR >60 mL/min/1.73 m² in isolation is not CKD, unless other evidence of kidney damage is present

CKD, chronic kidney disease; GFR, glomerular filtration rate

Materials and Methods

This descriptive study was conducted over a six-month period among patients diagnosed with CKD attending the outpatient department of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. A total of 70 patients aged above 18 years and above with confirmed CKD, defined as an eGFR < 90 mL/min/1.73m² for more than three months, were included. The estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was calculated using the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) formula. Exclusion criteria comprised patients with high myopia, corneal pathologies, vitreous or lens opacities interfering with fundus visualization, history of uveitis, glaucoma, or retinal diseases, and previous retinal laser treatments.

All subjects underwent a detailed ophthalmological assessment, including best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA), anterior segment evaluation by slit-lamp biomicroscopy, intraocular pressure (IOP) measurement using Goldmann applanation tonometry, and posterior segment examination with a 90-diopter lens. Systemic parameters such as blood pressure, BMI, serum creatinine, serum albumin, RFT, CRP, and urine albumin were also recorded. Mean arterial pressure (MAP) was calculated using the formula: $MAP = DBP + 1/3(SBP - DBP)$, as per standard guidelines [7].

Choroidal and retinal thickness measurements were obtained using spectral-domain OCT. Thickness was assessed in both inner and outer quadrants of retina and choroid in the macula (nasal, superior, temporal, and inferior) along with central thickness. For patients undergoing hemodialysis, imaging was performed 24 hours post-dialysis to avoid artefacts due to acute volume changes. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons across CKD stages were performed using one-way analysis of

variance (ANOVA), and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The baseline characteristics of the study population, as reflected in continuous variables, indicate a mean age of 44.71 years with a wide range (21–64 years), suggesting inclusion across adult age groups. The mean intraocular pressure (IOP) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) were within physiological ranges, averaging 16.77 mmHg and 108.27 mmHg, respectively. The average body mass index (BMI) was 21.54 kg/m², suggesting that the study population was predominantly in the normal weight range. Renal parameters showed significant variability, with an estimated

glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) ranging from 8 to 110 mL/min/1.73m² (mean 52.5), reflecting a spectrum of CKD severity. Serum albumin (mean 3.09 g/dL) and C-reactive protein (mean 9.5 mg/L) further reflected variable nutritional and inflammatory statuses. Retinal and choroidal thickness parameters, measured via swept source-domain OCT, displayed considerable variation, supporting the need for stratified analysis across CKD stages. The wide standard deviation in choroidal thickness (± 43.74 μ m) suggests a possible association with systemic disease burden. (Table 1)

The age distribution was fairly uniform across decades, with the largest group being 41–50 years (24.3%). Males constituted a slight majority (55.7%) of the study population. Hypertension was present in 55.7% of participants, indicating a common comorbidity among CKD patients. Regarding antihypertensive usage, 44.3% of subjects were not on any medications, while 35.7% were taking one agent. The sample was distributed across CKD stages, with Stages 2 and 5 having the highest representation (22.9% each), and Stage 4 being the least represented (15.7%). A majority (85.7%) of patients were not on dialysis at the time of assessment. Notably, 61.4% had no detectable urine albumin, while 31.4% showed trace amounts, suggesting early glomerular involvement in a significant portion. (Table 2)

Statistical comparison using one-way ANOVA revealed significant differences in chorioretinal parameters across CKD stages (all p-values < 0.001). A consistent and progressive decline was observed in total retinal thickness, from 275.57 μ m in Stage 1 to 243.19 μ m in Stage 5 (F = 33.68), supporting the hypothesis of CKD-related retinal thinning. Similar trends were evident across all inner and outer retinal quadrants. Notably, the temporal inner retina and inferior outer retina showed steep declines, indicating regional susceptibility. Choroidal thickness followed a similar trajectory, with total thickness reducing from 313.29 μ m in Stage 1 to 242.00 μ m in Stage 5 (F = 9.73). Among choroidal subfields, the inferior inner choroid exhibited the most marked thinning (F = 148.35), suggesting it may be particularly sensitive to systemic microvascular compromise. (Table 3)

Discussion

This study provides strong evidence that chorioretinal thinning correlates significantly with the severity of CKD. A progressive decline in retinal thickness was noted across the five CKD stages, with the most severe thinning observed in Stage 5. This supports previous observations by Paterson et al., who reported reduced inner retinal thickness in patients with CKD, especially in advanced stages [1]. The decline was uniform across inner and outer quadrants, with prominent reductions in the temporal and inferior regions, suggesting regional susceptibility.

The choroidal thickness showed even more dramatic changes. Inferior inner choroidal thickness, in particular, exhibited the greatest decline, consistent with the findings of Chang et al., who reported significant choroidal thinning post-hemodialysis [6]. The observed thinning may be attributed to systemic inflammation, increased sympathetic tone, and microvascular damage, as proposed by Vadalà et al. [3]. Additionally, our results align with the work of Kal et al., who showed no change in retinal thickness but significant reduction in choroidal thickness in hemodialysis patients [5].

Notably, systemic parameters such as IOP, MAP, and BMI did not show significant differences across CKD stages, thereby strengthening the hypothesis that the changes in ocular parameters are directly related to renal dysfunction. The significant association between reduced serum albumin, elevated CRP, and thinning of ocular structures further supports the role of systemic inflammation and poor nutritional status in ocular microvascular compromise.

The quadrant-wise OCT analysis performed in this study provides novel insights into region-specific patterns of thinning, which may have diagnostic and prognostic implications. This level of detail, coupled with adjustment for dialysis timing, enhances the robustness of our findings and provides a foundation for further longitudinal and interventional studies.

Furthermore, our findings align with Basiony et al., who observed that retinal and choroidal thinning is significantly associated with CKD stages 3 to 5. Their results also revealed no association with hypertension, but a strong negative correlation between CRP and albuminuria with choroidal thickness. These findings suggest a possible contribution of systemic inflammation and autonomic nervous system disturbances to the observed choroidal changes [8,9].

The involvement of autonomic imbalance, particularly increased sympathetic activity seen in CKD, has been proposed to explain choroidal thinning, since the choroidal circulation is richly innervated unlike the retinal vasculature [9]. Prior studies, including those by Vadalà et al. [3] and Yeung et al. [4], using SS-OCT and OCTA, further substantiated our findings by demonstrating decreased vascular density, increased vascular tortuosity, and retinal non-perfusion in CKD.

Our findings are also consistent with those of Wu et al., who reported that advanced CKD stages are associated with retinal neural impairment, and with Chang et al., who demonstrated body weight loss-related choroidal thinning in hemodialysis patients [10,11]. The physiological mechanisms underlying these changes may involve alterations in plasma colloid osmotic pressure, serum osmolality, and interstitial fluid shifts during dialysis [12].

Majithia et al. have emphasized that shared microvascular mechanisms, including oxidative stress and renin-angiotensin system (RAS) dysregulation, underpin both kidney and retinal damage. Given that the RAS is locally active in the retina as well

as the kidneys, dysregulation may exacerbate neuroretinal thinning in CKD patients. These pathways may also explain thinning of retinal nerve fiber layers (RNFL) and ganglion cell-inner plexiform layer (GCIPL) observed in both CKD and glaucoma, warranting careful monitoring of these parameters [9,13-15].

Conclusion

Our study demonstrates a significant and proportional reduction in both retinal and choroidal thickness with advancing stages of chronic kidney disease. These structural changes, detectable through spectral-domain OCT, may serve as valuable non-invasive biomarkers for systemic microvascular health. Given the systemic nature of CKD and its impact on the ocular microvasculature, ophthalmic evaluation could play a supportive role in the multidisciplinary care of CKD patients. Future research should explore the predictive value of these changes and their potential role in guiding systemic management strategies.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Continuous Variables in the Study Population

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	21	64	44.71	13.337
sex	1	2	1.44	0.500
IOP(mm hg)	10	22	16.77	3.592
MAP	81	119	108.27	6.487
BMI	18	25	21.54	2.124
eGFR	8	110	52.50	34.893
S.Albumin	2.2	3.9	3.094	0.4014
CRP	3.5	18.3	9.501	3.8332
Retinal central thickness	222	284	260.67	15.044
Nasal inner RT	300	327	312.53	5.581
Superior inner RT	300	321	312.07	4.048
Temporal inner RT	294	319	308.13	5.951
Inferior inner RT	299	320	312.34	4.117
Nasal outer RT	281	300	287.67	3.756
superior outer RT	281	301	288.47	4.353
Temporal outer RT	259	291	277.59	6.689
Inferior outer RT	271	290	283.51	3.821
Choroidal central thickness	185	347	263.40	43.741
Nasal inner CT	250	339	295.36	21.031
Superior inner CT	295	380	338.04	24.406
Temporal inner CT	271	355	306.60	20.992
Inferior inner CT	251	379	322.54	33.672
Nasal outer CT	250	330	290.34	18.254
superior outer CT	254	364	311.33	27.344

Temporal outer CT	245	335	283.49	23.986
Inferior outer CT	245	355	300.47	25.990

Table 2: Distribution of Categorical Variables in the Study Population

Parameter	Subclassification	F	%
AGE	21-30	15.0	21.4
	31-40	12.0	17.1
	41-50	17.0	24.3
	51-60	14.0	20.1
	>60	14.0	17.1
SEX	Male	39	55.7
	Female	31	44.3
Hypertension	Yes	39	55.7
	No	31	44.3
No of antihypertensives taken	0	31	44.3
	1	25	35.7
	2	12	17.1
	3	2	2.9
CKD Stage	1	14	20.0
	2	16	22.9
	3	13	18.6
	4	11	15.7
	5	16	22.9
Dialysis	Yes	10	14.3
	No	60	85.7
Urine Albumin	0	43	61.4
	1	22	31.4
	2	5	7.1

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Chorioretinal Thickness Across CKD Stages Using One-Way ANOVA

Parameter measured	CKD Stage										F value	P Value
	1		2		3		4		5			
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
RETINAL THICKNESS												
Central thickness	275.57	5.56	271	7.26	260.77	6.51	252	11.78	243.19	11.53	33.68	<0.001
Nasal inner RT	306	4.21	309.25	3.19	314.77	2.52	315.64	2.66	317.56	4.27	27.21	<0.001
Superior inner RT	309.64	1.91	310.5	3.58	310.15	4.36	314.27	2.53	315.81	3.19	10.63	<0.001
Temporal inner RT	309.21	3.47	315.38	2.63	309.23	2.42	304.91	3.53	301.25	4.04	40.46	<0.001
Inferior inner RT	315.29	2.3	314.19	2.17	310.69	3.28	312.55	4.97	309.12	4.3	7.74	<0.001
Nasal outer RT	284.64	2.34	286.12	2.16	289.62	2.96	288	2.79	290.06	4.77	7.54	<0.001
superior outer RT	285.36	1.86	287.31	1.96	287.15	4.12	289.09	3.83	293	4.77	10.47	<0.001
Temporal outer RT	284.07	2.87	280	2.85	275.69	6.71	279.18	4.56	269.94	5.27	19.73	<0.001
Inferior outer RT	286.29	2.52	285.94	1.84	283.92	1.93	281.09	5.3	280	2.34	13.98	<0.001
CHOROIDAL THICKNESS												
central thickness	313.29	13.5	265.19	44.74	241.31	35.43	254.55	38.75	242	36.61	9.73	<0.001
Nasal inner CT	321.36	11.69	306.75	11.83	285.54	10.02	289.18	10.8	273.44	14.99	35.31	<0.001
Superior inner CT	365.71	12.48	355.44	17.43	322.46	12.53	328.91	15	315.38	12.99	34.18	<0.001
Temporal inner CT	333.07	12.2	314.62	10.68	297.46	13.28	308.64	7.59	281.44	11.44	43.25	<0.001
Inferior inner CT	368.36	9.42	346.56	8.91	301.54	11.07	311.36	4.06	283.19	15.8	148.35	<0.001
Nasal outer CT	304.43	16.08	287	10.56	284.23	13.06	301.82	11.04	278.44	22.41	7.35	<0.001
superior outer CT	345.14	14.94	323.62	13.54	306.46	21.45	294.91	16.71	284.69	17.45	28.98	<0.001
Temporal outer CT	310.36	14.63	285.88	29.45	278.92	9.95	273.64	17.28	268.06	17.1	10.24	<0.001
Inferior outer CT	326.79	19.87	310.12	10.55	291.15	20.59	298.64	21.53	276.62	23.99	13.85	<0.001